

Minor as a special subject of law and civil protection: international and national experience

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Abstract. The article, based on the norms of international conventions and the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, examines the status of a minor as a subject of civil law, and also defines the types of civil protection of the rights of a minor.

Keywords: minor, subject of civil law, civil protection.

Human rights begin with the rights of the child, and by guaranteeing these rights, each state ensures its future. Currently, the world's population exceeds 8 billion people, of which 34% are children under 14 years of age [1]. Thus, ensuring sufficient guarantees of children's rights, ensuring their civil and family rights and developing organizational and legal mechanisms for the implementation of these rights are urgent tasks. Consequently, guaranteed children's rights are the main criterion for their upbringing and development. In the context of globalization and significant penetration of the virtual world into the lives of children, problematic aspects of guarantees of their rights become obvious. Therefore, the creation of a system of guarantees of children's rights that can withstand modern challenges and threats, as well as make a worthy contribution to their upbringing and development, is an urgent need.

Minors are a unique and vulnerable category of legal entities with a special legal status, which is determined by their age and level of psychophysical development. In the context of legal theory and civil protection, minors require a special approach that takes into account their limited legal capacity and legal capacity. In this chapter we will examine the theoretical foundations of the legal capacity of minors, analyze the existing legal mechanisms for protecting their property rights, and evaluate various methodological approaches to the study and improvement of this area.

Legal capacity of minors is a set of rights and obligations that can be exercised by minors within the framework of legal relations[2]. Legal capacity includes legal capacity and legal competence, which are determined by the age and level of maturity of the individual. It is important to note that legal capacity arises from the moment of birth, while legal capacity develops gradually as the individual grows older and reaches certain age stages.

There are various approaches to the classification and interpretation of legal

capacity of minors in the literature. Thus, legal capacity can be divided into general and special. General legal capacity includes basic rights that are recognized for all minors (for example, the right to life, health, education), while special legal capacity includes rights that can be exercised only upon reaching a certain age or level of maturity (for example, the right to participate in civil transactions) [3].

The legal protection of minors is based on a number of fundamental principles and theories that determine the nature and content of legal norms governing their rights and interests. Let us consider some of these principles and theories in more detail.

The principle of the best interests of the child is one of the key principles underlying the legal protection of minors. According to this principle, all decisions concerning children must be made taking into account their best interests. This principle was first enshrined in the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child and is fundamental to all legal systems seeking to ensure the protection of children's rights. The principle of the best interests of the child assumes that all actions and decisions taken by government bodies, judicial authorities, parents or legal representatives must be aimed at ensuring the maximum benefit and well-being of the child[4].

This principle not only emphasizes the importance of protecting the interests of children, but also creates a basis for the development and application of legal norms that take into account the specific needs and characteristics of minors.

The principle of equality and non-discrimination is fundamental in the legal protection of minors. This principle assumes that all children, regardless of their gender, race, nationality, social origin or other characteristics, have equal rights and should receive equal protection from the state. The principle of equality and non-discrimination is enshrined in various international legal instruments, such as the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child, and is an integral part of national legal systems. The principle of children's participation in decision-making emphasizes the importance of taking into account the opinions and interests of children when making decisions that affect their lives and well-being[5].

This principle assumes that children have the right to express their opinions on all issues affecting their interests, and these opinions must be taken into account when making decisions. The principle of children's participation in decision-making promotes the development of a sense of responsibility and understanding of their rights and responsibilities in children, as well as the formation of legal awareness and legal culture. Children's participation in decision-making not only contributes to their legal education, but is also an important element of a democratic society, where the interests of all its members, including the youngest, are taken into account[6].

The principle of legal certainty and predictability plays an important role in ensuring the legal protection of minors. This principle assumes that legal norms should be clear, clearly formulated and predictable in their application. Legal certainty and predictability ensure stability and consistency of law enforcement practice, which is especially important

for the protection of the rights and interests of minors.

Thus, the protection of the property rights of minors is an important part of the legal system aimed at protecting and ensuring the rights and interests of children in the sphere of property relations. Legal regulation of the protection of the property rights of minors includes both international and national legal acts that establish the basic principles and mechanisms of protection.

International standards for the protection of the property rights of minors are enshrined in various international legal acts, such as the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child, the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, as well as other international documents. These acts establish the basic principles and standards for the protection of children's rights, including their property rights, and oblige member states to take the necessary measures to implement them.

Thus, the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child[7], adopted by the UN General Assembly on 20 November 1989, is a fundamental international document regulating the rights of children. The Convention defines a child as a person under the age of 18 and recognizes the full range of human rights for children, including civil, political, economic, social and cultural rights. An important aspect of the Convention is the obligation of States Parties to protect the property rights of children.

Article 3 of the Convention enshrines the principle of the best interests of the child, according to which in all actions concerning children, whether carried out by public or private institutions, courts, administrative bodies or legislative bodies, the best interests of the child must be a primary consideration. This means that the property rights of children must be protected and taken into account in any decisions concerning their property.

Article 27 of the Convention provides that States Parties recognize the right of every child to a standard of living adequate for his or her physical, mental, spiritual, moral and social development. Parents or others responsible for the child have the primary responsibility to ensure conditions of living necessary for the child's development, and States undertake to take all appropriate measures to assist parents and others to realize this right.

The UN Convention on the Rights of the Child also highlights the importance of protecting children's property rights. For example, Article 5 requires States to respect the responsibilities, rights and duties of parents or, where applicable, members of the extended family or community as provided for by local custom, guardians or other persons legally responsible for the child, to provide adequate guidance and ensure the implementation of the child's rights in accordance with the evolving capacities of the child. This provision highlights the need to support families in the management and protection of minors' property rights.

The European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms[8], adopted by the Council of Europe in 1950, also contains provisions concerning the protection of minors' property rights. Article 1 of Protocol No. 1 to the

Convention establishes the right of every natural or legal person to the peaceful enjoyment of his or her possessions. Although this right is not absolute and may be subject to certain limitations, it provides protection against arbitrary interference with property rights by the State.

In addition to the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child and the European Convention on Human Rights, there are a number of other international documents that set out standards for the protection of the property rights of minors. For example, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) and the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR) contain provisions concerning the rights of children and their protection. The International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, adopted by the UN General Assembly in 1966 and entered into force in 1976[9], recognizes in Article 10 that “the widest protection and assistance should be accorded to the family, which is the natural and fundamental group unit of society, particularly during its formation and while it is responsible for the care and education of dependent children.” This provision emphasizes the importance of protecting the property rights of minors within the framework of family relations and the duties of the state to ensure such protection.

States parties to international treaties are obliged to take all necessary measures to protect the property rights of minors. This includes the development and adoption of national legislation, the creation of effective legal and administrative mechanisms, and ensuring access of children and their legal representatives to justice and legal assistance.

According to experts, state bodies must take active measures to ensure legal protection of the property rights of minors, including monitoring and control over compliance with these rights, as well as taking measures to prevent and suppress violations. States must also ensure legal education and informing parents, guardians and children themselves about their rights and mechanisms for their protection.

Thus, international standards for the protection of the property rights of minors, enshrined in various international legal acts, play an important role in ensuring the safety and well-being of children. These standards require states parties to take the necessary measures to implement children's rights, including the development of national legislation, the creation of effective legal and administrative mechanisms, and access to justice and legal assistance. Compliance with international standards is an important condition for the formation of a fair and sustainable legal system that ensures the protection of the property rights and interests of minors.

National legal acts regulating the protection of property rights of minors include civil codes, laws on children's rights, laws on guardianship and trusteeship, as well as other regulations aimed at protecting the property interests of children. These acts establish the procedure for managing the property of minors, the conditions and procedure for making transactions with their property, as well as measures of responsibility for violations in this area.

Thus, according to national legislation, minors are citizens under 18 years of age. (The Civil Code defines the legal capacity of children aged 14 to 18 years). Based on the Civil Code (Article 27) [10], these persons have the right to independently, without the consent of parents, adoptive parents and guardians:

- 1) receive wages, scholarships, etc., dispose of income;
- 2) exercise copyrights to a work of science, literature or art, an invention or other result of their intellectual activity protected by law;
- 3) placing deposits in credit institutions and managing them in accordance with the law;
- 4) to carry out small business transactions and other transactions, they conclude other transactions with the written consent of their parents, adoptive parents or guardians.

With their consent and in the presence of certain circumstances, a child who has reached the age of 16 may be declared fully capable (Articles 27, 28, 29 of the Civil Code). The Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan provides guarantees of employment and equal rights for persons under the age of 18[11]. Also, commissions on minors have been created under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, regional, city and district khokimiyats.

The property rights of minors were not reflected in previous laws. Now they are given a proper place in Article 90 of the Family Code[12].

According to Article 90 of the Family Code, minors have the right to receive alimony from their parents and other persons in the amount and in the manner prescribed by law. Funds, pensions, alimony received for the maintenance of minor children are at the disposal of the father or mother and must be spent on the maintenance, upbringing and education of the child. In addition, children have such a property right as receiving property as a gift. This is a traditional and very common way of acquiring real estate. Such property can be acquired not only from relatives, but also from other individuals and even legal entities.

According to Article 29 of the Civil Code, contracts with minors (young children) under the age of fourteen, with the exception of those specified in Part Two of this Article, may be concluded only by their parents, adoptive parents or guardians[10].

As already noted, today in our country special attention is paid to the radical improvement of the institutional and legal foundations for the reliable protection of the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of children, early prevention of lack of control and crimes among children. These measures are aimed at creating favorable conditions for the development and upbringing of minors, as well as ensuring their protection from possible threats and violations[13,14,15].

In particular, the Institute of Children's Ombudsman and the Republican Interdepartmental Commission on Minors' Affairs have been created. The legal framework for regulating public relations in this sphere is being strengthened, and the current legislation is being improved. The Ombudsman is independent in his decisions and

monitors compliance with children's rights, considers complaints and appeals, conducts investigations and interacts with government and public organizations to resolve problems related to violations of the rights of minors[16,17,18,19].

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